

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF TiO₂/GRAPHENE HYBRID BY SOL-GEL PROCESS ASSISTED WITH MICROWAVE IRRADIATION

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1 Introduction

Graphene, a two-dimensional sp² carbon network, has attracted much attention due to its superior electrical, mechanical, and thermal properties. It has been studied for various applications as reinforcements, conductive fillers, and functional materials due to its high surface area, charge carrier mobility, mechanical flexibility, and optical transparency [1, 2]. It is also used as substrates for nanostructured metal or semiconductor metal oxide nanoparticles of Pt, Au, Ag, and TiO₂ for catalytic applications [3-5]

Titanium dioxide is very popular and widely used in many applications as photovoltaic, catalyst, battery, and hydrogen production because of its nontoxic nature, low cost with wide band gap, and high photocatalytic activity [6, 7]. Various methods have been studied to enhance the photocatalytic and photoelectrochemical performances of TiO₂ in metal particle loadings, co-catalysts, dye sensitization, and metallic or non metallic doping [8]. Recently, the hybrid of TiO₂ with carbonous nano materials (CNM) especially carbon nanotube and graphene have been investigated to enhance performance of TiO₂ because of their unique and controllable structure and electrical properties. The significant enhancements of photocatalytic and photoelectrochemical behavior of the hybrid of CNT or graphene with TiO₂ have been reported. The enhancement may be due to the following possibility: the band-gap turning, retardation of electron-hole recombination, provision of high

surface area for absorption of reactant and active site [5, 9-11].

Methods reported to prepare the hybrids of TiO₂/CNM can be classified into three. The first is simple mixing of nanocrystalline TiO₂ with CNM [9], usually resulting in rather heterogenous dispersion of TiO₂ nanoparticles on the surface of CNM. The second is sol-gel calcinations process. Amorphous TiO₂ deposited on the surface of CNM were calcinated at high temperature over 400 °C for several hours in order to form nano crystalline TiO₂ [10]. Both rutile and anatase TiO₂ can be obtained by this process. The third is hydrothermal process in which the hybrid of crystalline TiO₂/CNM is prepared in autoclave reactor at high pressure for several hours to crystallize TiO₂ [5]. Usually only nanoparticles of anatase TiO₂ are formed on the surface of graphene in the hydrothermal processes. However, those processes employ the conventional heating for several hours and high pressure.

Microwave is popular in industries as well as in household applications because of direct and fast heating with high efficiency. By microwave irradiation for short time, nanocrystalline TiO₂ is formed homogenously and effectively [6]. Moreover, graphene is also prepared rapidly from graphite oxide (GO) under microwave irradiation [2]. Taking into account of the advantages of microwave irradiations, we studied a new, simple, and effective method to prepare TiO₂/graphene hybrid from GO and titanium precursor by microwave irradiation. The effects of TiO₂ content and microwave radiation time on the properties of TiO₂/graphene hybrids are reported in this paper.

Scheme 1. Typical process to prepare TiO₂/Graphene hybrids.

Figure 1. Morphological features of GO prepared: (a) TEM image; (b) AFM image; (c) Height profile in (b).

2 Experimental details

2.1 Material and preparation

Synthetic graphite particle and titanium tetrapropoxide (TTP, reagent grade) from Aldrich Chemical were used without further purification. GO were prepared by modified Hummer method [12]. The process to prepare TiO₂/graphene hybrids is summarized in Scheme 1. Typically, 0.4 g of GO was dispersed in 400ml of DMF and 1.42g of TTP were added followed by ultrasonication for 4 hours to obtain homogenous solution. Excess amount of deionized water were added dropwise under rigorous stirring for 1 hour. Then centrifuge, washing with deionized water, and drying were carried out to get powders of amorphous TiO₂/GO. Finally, nanocrystalline TiO₂/Graphene hybrids were obtained by irradiating the powder in a conventional microwave oven (Samsung Electronics, 750W) for different periods. The compositions and irradiation time is shown in Table 1.

2.2 Characterization

GO and the hybrids of TiO₂/graphene were characterized employing a X-ray diffractometer

(XRD), X'pert PRO MRD from Philips, using Cu K α radiation and operating at 30kV and 13 mA, FTIR spectrometer (JASCO 4100), high resolution transmittance electron microscopy (HR-TEM, JEOL JEM-2010), and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), AXIS-NOVA (Kratos. Inc).

Table 1. Sample codes for TiO₂/graphene hybrids of different compositions and microwave irradiation times

Sample Codes	TTP/GO ratio	Irradiation time (second)	TiO ₂ content ^a (%)	A/R ratio
TiO ₂	0	30'	0	
GT1	1.77	30'	55.8	0.36
GT2	3.55	30'	70.5	0.28
GT3	7.10	30'	86.7	0.39
GT4	14.2	30'	87.1	0.43
GT5	3.55	30'+20'	75.3	0.29
GT6	3.55	30'+60'	83.7	0.55

a: TiO₂ content obtained from TGA data of the hybrids after microwave irradiation.

3 Results and discussion

Figure 1 shows TEM and AFM images of GO prepared by modified Hummer's methods. After

ultrasonication in DMF, thin layers of GO were obtained as shown in Figure 1. In Figure 1(c), the thickness of GO is about 3.1nm (two layers of GO sheet). FTIR spectra of GO is shown in Figure 2(a). The broad peak from 3000cm^{-1} to 3600cm^{-1} is attributed to stretching of hydroxyl groups. The characteristic peaks at 1730cm^{-1} , 1620cm^{-1} and 1212cm^{-1} correspond to stretching of carbonyl (C=O), skeletal vibration of unoxidized graphitic domains and stretching of C-OH respectively [13]. Figure 2(b) shows the IR spectrum of TTP with characteristic peaks of CH_2 and CH_3 (around 2850cm^{-1} - 3000cm^{-1}). After TTP was added into GO, the broad peak of hydroxyl group in GO disappeared (Figure 2(c)). It is due to the exchange reaction of TTP with OH groups of GO (scheme 1), making GO more stable in DMF solution. The spectrum of pure TiO_2 in Figure 2(d) shows characteristic peaks of hydroxyl groups at 3270cm^{-1} , and water absorbed at 1623cm^{-1} . No characteristic peaks of GO or TTP were observed in the spectrum of $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Graphene}$ after microwave irradiation for 30 seconds (Figure 2(e)). The results indicate that after hydrolysis and microwave irradiation, TTP was converted into TiO_2 and GO were reduced to graphene [2].

Figure 3 shows TEM images of TiO_2/GO and $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Graphene}$. Before microwave irradiation, the layer of amorphous TiO_2 covered the surface of GO as shown in Figure 3(a). After microwave irradiation (30 seconds), the nanoparticles of TiO_2 in range of 20 nm were homogenously formed on the surface of graphene (Figure 3(b)). The crystal structure of TiO_2 (green arrows) and few layers structure of graphene (red arrows) were observed in HR-TEM image of $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Graphene}$ (Figure 3(c)). Those results indicate that crystalline TiO_2 nanoparticles were formed by microwave irradiation.

Figure 3. TEM images of GT2: (a) after hydrolysis; (b) after microwave irradiation; (c) HR-TEM image of GT2.

Figure 2. FTIR spectra of GO (a), TTP (b), TTP modified GO (c), TiO_2 (d), and $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Graphene}$.

Figure 4. XRD data of GT2 before microwave irradiation (a), GT1 (b), GT2 (c), GT3 (d), GT4 (e) after microwave irradiations.

Figure 4 shows XRD patterns of TiO_2/GO and $\text{TiO}_2/\text{graphene}$ hybrids. Before microwave irradiation, no characteristic diffraction peak of crystalline TiO_2 was observed, indicating amorphous nature of TiO_2 ((a) in Figure 4). After microwave

irradiation for 30 seconds, no characteristic diffraction peak of TiO₂ crystal structures were observed in the sample containing only amorphous TiO₂. On the other hand, the characteristic diffraction peaks corresponding to mixture of rutile and anatase structures of TiO₂ were observed on the samples containing GO under microwave irradiation ((b)~(e) in Figure 4). Szeifert *et al.* reported that, under microwave irradiation, the rate of formation of crystalline TiO₂ could be enhanced significantly [6]. It is postulated that GO absorbed microwave and heated the system to high temperature where the crystalline TiO₂ were formed. Employing the following Debye-Scherrer equation [14], the ratios of Anatase/Rutile (A/R) were calculated and given in Table 1.

$$\beta = 1/[1+1.26I_R/I_A] \quad (1)$$

where β is ratio of Anatase/Rutile, I_R , I_A is peak diffraction intensity of rutile and anatase, respectively. With increase the ratio of TiO₂/GO the ratio of A/R decreased and then increased. The change of A/R is attributable to different GO content, resulting in different microwave absorption and temperature rise.

Figure 5 shows XDR patterns of TiO₂/graphene hybrids with different irradiation time. After 30 seconds irradiation ((a) in Figure 5), the A/R ratio of the hybrid was 0.28. After additional microwave irradiation time of 20 seconds ((b) in Figure 5) and 60 seconds ((c) in Figure 5), the A/R ratio increased from 0.28 to 0.29 and 0.55 respectively. It is generally known that at high temperature the changing from anatase to rutile in TiO₂ is favorable in bulk state. But in nano scale, thermodynamically, the TiO₂ in rutile structure is less stable than that in anatase, therefore changing from rutile to anatase structure is favorable [15].

It is interesting to observe in Figure 5(c) the appearance of 2 θ peak at 42.5 degree corresponding to the formation of lower oxidation state of titanium such as Ti₂O₃ or TiO. During the additional microwave irradiation for 60 seconds, the hybrid became bright red-hot, implying that the temperature of the hybrid might reach more than 1000 °C. At high temperature and in the presence of carbon as reducing agent, the reduction of TiO₂ to form lower oxidation state of Ti₂O₃ or TiO can occur [16]. It is reported that the Ti₂O₃ or TiO have lower band gap

than TiO₂, and more conductive than TiO₂. Thus, much attention was paid to their applications in photo catalysts and solar cells [8, 16].

Figure 5. XRD data of: (a) GT2; (b) GT5; (c) GT6.

Figure 6. XPS data of C1s of: (a) GO; (b) GT2; (c) GT6

Figure 7. XPS data of Ti(2p) of: (a) GT2; (b) GT6

Figure 6 shows C1s XPS data of GO and TiO₂/graphene hybrids. It is clearly observed in

Figure 6(a) that the strong broad binding energy peak from 285eV to 290eV are corresponding to the C-O and C=O bonds of GO. In Figure 6(b), after 30 seconds of microwave irradiation, the binding energy peak of C=O and C-O were depressed significantly, indicating that GO were reduced under microwave irradiation [10]. In Figure 6(c), by microwave irradiation for additional 60 seconds, the peaks of C=O and C-O peaks were further depressed due to the reduction of GO.

Figure 7 shows XPS Ti(2p) data of TiO₂/graphene hybrids after different microwave irradiation periods. In Figure 7(a), the characteristic binding energy peaks due to Ti(2p_{1/2}) and Ti(2p_{3/2}) of TiO₂ were observed at 464.8eV and 459eV, respectively. In Figure 7(b), after additional microwave irradiation for 60 seconds, the blue shifts of binding energy peaks were observed. It is attributable to the formation of lower oxidation state of TiO₂ (Ti₂O₃ or TiO) [8,17]. These results observed with XPS agree well with the results found in XRD data.

Figure 8 shows TEM images of various TiO₂/graphene obtained from the different ratio of TTP/GO and different irradiation time. The TEM image of GT1 under 30 seconds microwave irradiation is shown in Figure 8(a). The nanoparticles with average diameter of 8 nm were observed and dispersed separately on the graphene

sheets. At the same irradiation time, with increasing the TTP/GO ratio (GT2~GT4), the diameter of TiO₂ particles increased from 8 nm to 13 nm, 19 nm and 20 nm, respectively (Figure 8(b-d)). Moreover, it is observed that the number of particle per unit area increase proportionally as the concentrations of TTP was increased. At the fixed ratio of TTP/GO, the diameters of TiO₂ particles slightly increased with the increase of microwave irradiation time (Figure 8(b, e, f)).

In order to determine the TiO₂ content in the hybrids after microwave irradiation, the TGA were performed in the air and the results were also shown in Table 1. It is clearly observed that with increase the ratio of TTP/GO the TiO₂ content in the hybrids increased proportionally. Furthermore, the TiO₂ content in TiO₂/graphene hybrids obtained by TGA is much larger than the TiO₂ content in TiO₂/GO calculated from the contents of TTP and GO. It is believed that the difference is due to the weight loss of GO during the reduction under microwave irradiation. At the same ratio of TTP/GO, the TiO₂ content increased with increasing microwave irradiation periods due to the reduction of GO.

4 Conclusion

Thin layer of Graphite oxide were successfully prepared by modified Hummer's method. The

Figure 8. TEM image of the hybrids: (a) GT1, (b) GT2, (c) GT3, (d) GT4, (e) GT5, (e) GT6,

hybrids of TiO₂/graphene were successfully prepared from GO and TTP by a simple and effective method under the assistance of microwave irradiation. Without GO or microwave irradiation, amorphous TiO₂ were formed. By microwave irradiation of amorphous TiO₂ for short time (30 seconds) in the present of GO, GO were reduced in to graphene and the mixture of anatase and rutile in nanoparticles of TiO₂ were obtained. The ratios of A/R could be controlled by varying the ratio of TTP/GO or the period of microwave irradiation. We also found that lower oxidation state of TiO₂ (Ti₂O₃ or TiO) could be observed after 90 seconds of microwave irradiation totally.

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